
THE ACCEPTABILITY OF ONLINE LEARNING ACTION CELL SESSION PRACTICE TO TAGUMPAY NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative study explores the acceptability of Online Learning Action Cell (LAC) practice as a school-based professional development strategy for Tagumpay National High School (TNHS) teachers. The research was motivated by the Department of Education (DepEd) Order No. 35 s. 2016 which prompts public schools to comply with the implementation of LAC sessions because it has a positive impact on teachers' beliefs and practices resulting in education reforms for learners' benefit. However, in compliance with DepEd's policy on maximizing Time-On-Task (DepEd Order No. 9 s. 2005) and the teacher's conflict of schedule and other ancillary and coordination functions, absences or non-participation in classroom LAC was noted. The viability of offering Online LAC sessions using appropriate media and technologies to provide more options and flexibility for the study is suggested and tested utilizing a conceptual framework drawn from DepEd Order No. 35 s. 2016, Simonson's Equivalency Theory and Anderson's Community of Inquiry (COI). A descriptive survey method was used in this study with purposive sampling identifying ten Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers to pilot the Online LAC based on the memorandum issued by the school head. The subjects went through a week of experience in a LAC session using Facebook (FB) as Learning Management System (LMS) while a researcher-designed survey tool in the form of a Likert-type scale questionnaire was administered via Google forms before and after the online session to measure teacher's acceptability of Online LAC Session practice. In the analysis, a descriptive statistic shows that pre-post survey results on Online LAC session planning is from 'moderately acceptable' to 'very highly acceptable'; implementation is from 'acceptable' to 'very highly acceptable', and evaluation is from 'moderately acceptable' to 'very highly acceptable'. TNHS teachers' acceptability of Online LAC session practice increases after their participation in a fully-online learning environment. Limitations, recommendations, future research directions, and conclusions are also included in the study.

Keywords: Online Learning Action Cell session, Tagumpay National High School, LAC

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INTRODUCTION

The changing face of education led to higher demand for quality teaching workforce resulting in a shift in teachers' role inside the classroom. This demand drives teachers to adjust, localize and diversify their strategies to attend to a multicultural classroom that caters to students with special and varying needs. In addition, the integration of information and communication technologies (ICTs) was intensified not only in teaching and learning but also in curriculum planning, assessment, and reporting (OECD, 2009). In consideration of these demands which are also classified as teacher's needs, DepEd recognizes the importance of quality teaching through quality learning by supporting teachers in their development, in the teaching profession, by establishing professional learning communities (also known as teachers quality circle or community of practice) as a school-based professional development strategy. Article I section 2 of DepEd Order No. 35 s. 2016 affirms that teachers' participation in professional development activities has a positive impact on teachers' belief and practices, students' learning, and the implementation of educational reforms (UNESCO ISO, 2006). The changing face of education was also attributed to technology revolution resulting to unceasing study, improvement, and adoption of information, tools, processes, and resources that significantly affect teaching and learning. As education continuously transform and respond to teachers' changing needs, the information and communication technologies (ICTs) products and services are likewise developing and expanding to their advantage. The idea is to capitalize on ICT affordances as to promote an accessible form of continuous flexible education that is tailored to teachers' needs, cost-effective, offers convenience, accessible anytime, anywhere and could adopt any class size.

Part of these needs is teachers' involvement in a Continuing Professional Development (CPD). CPD is not a new concept to Tagumpay National High School (TNHS). Founded on 2003, TNHS is one of DepEd's junior public high school located in the second district of Rodriguez, Rizal and has since been promoting teacher's continuous development and the use of ICT as a tool for continuous learning. TNHS' CPDs are evident by the school's curriculum enhancement programs such as in-service training for teachers (INSET) and school-based initiated and localized seminars/trainings/workshops, and provision of training support to teachers through fund allocation from the school's Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) and/or local school fund. These are the school's commitment to lifelong learning and continuing education. However, policies impose the alignment of CPD programs to DepEd's rule instituting measures to increase engaged time-on-task (DepEd Order No. 9 s. 2005) where it requires teachers and/or students to maximize time allotment for every subject and discourage any form of class disruptions including teachers' physical participation to seminars/trainings/workshops during school days unless planned, communicated and necessary.

Background and Purpose of the Study

On June 7, 2016, DepEd has issued a policy on "The Learning Action Cell (LAC) as a K to 12 Basic Education Program School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning" (DepEd Order No. 35, s 2016). The LAC is designed to improve teachers content knowledge, pedagogical skills, assessment strategies, and professional ethics. LAC sessions can also be used to introduce new concepts and ideas for discussion based on the competencies of K to 12 Basic Education program. Hence, promoting CPD based on the principles of lifelong learning and DepEd's commitment to the development of teacher's potential aimed towards their success.

A strict compliance with this order prompt TNHS, with its eight (8) departments and eighty-two (82) teachers, to regularly implement the classroom-based LAC session/s in the same year. LAC session is done at least once a month (can be more frequent) depending on teacher's needs, that lasts one up to two hours each session. However, based on the data collected at TNHS, several factors affect LAC session practice, one prominent reason that was recorded is the teacher's absence and lack of participation due to conflict of schedule and workload.

Policy statement of DO 35, s. 2016 mentions that good educational systems ensure that opportunities for professional development programs are available and accessible to teachers for the benefit of the learners. In line with availability and accessibility, online education or e-learning is perceived as a

solution to the ongoing conflicts of schedule because of the flexibility it offers, wherein learners are in control and can manage their study time (Toufaily & Lee, 2018).

This study explores the viability of offering a school-based professional development or LAC session in an online mode to offer teachers more flexible options for studying. Specifically, research purpose is focused on TNHS teacher's acceptability of LAC session's practice as implemented by DepEd when offered in a fully-online mode of learning.

The following questions guided this research:

1. How acceptable is Online LAC session "*planning*" to TNHS teachers?
2. How acceptable is Online LAC session "*implementation*" to TNHS teachers?
3. How acceptable is Online LAC session "*evaluation*" to TNHS teachers?
4. Do TNHS teacher's acceptability of Online LAC session "*planning, implementation and evaluation*" change after their participation?

Literature Review

Online Continuing Professional Development (CPD) started to gain grounds due to the flexibility it offers by allowing participants, irrespective of location, to update, improve, expand their skills, and manage educational pursuits with work and personal responsibilities (Vu, et. al, 2014). In an attempt to find teachers perception of online CPD, three previous articles were identified to explain the factors that contribute to its acceptability.

Garbe (2012) studied teacher's perception of online professional development in literacy. The online professional development that the teachers went through was based on a theoretical model developed by the National Staff Development Council (NSDC). This model contains factors of "Effective Professional Development Influence" such as content focus, collectivity, coherence, duration and active learning, and highlights the interplay of online professional development with teaching capacity, reading instruction, and student learning. He then gathered three participant's data from logs, interview, and surveys and analyze/categorize their response under the key factors established by NSDC. The findings revealed that two literature teacher's perception of online PD reflected the five factors of effective PD and one participant reportedly perceived online PD to have four of five features.

In another study, Tong et. al (2015) used a qualitative survey response data from 75 third grade bilingual teachers in a randomized control trial (RCT) to examine teachers' perceptions towards the project's virtual professional development (VPD). VPD is curriculum-based and delivered via Citrix GoToTraining with the integrated web, audio, and HD video conferencing capabilities, to provide a complete collaboration experience in a single interface. Reviewing the responses of participants, theme categories were identified such as convenience, content, delivery, and technology difficulties. The positive response from this category was 79% while dissenting is 21%.

Lastly, Powell & Bodur (2019) examined teachers' perceptions of online professional development experience in the context of high school social studies. The participants underwent a job-embedded online PD which utilized 360, an online video library through which they're required to watch 10 video-based modules and respond to three open-ended reflective follow-up questions per video. Using a qualitative study, participants reveal the importance of specific design and implementation features of online professional development which includes relevancy, authenticity, usefulness, collaboration and interaction, reflection and context.

Analysis of the literature has significantly revealed teacher's acceptability of online CPD based from different factors (characteristics of effective PD, themes response, design, and implementation) and contexts (social studies, literature, bilingual). The factors that contribute to the acceptability depends on the nature, design, and strategy of a certain online professional development program they have experienced. Though the components of online CPD such as flexibility, enhancement of skills, professional development and mediation of technology is present (Garbe, 2012; Tong et. al, 2015; Powell & Bodur, 2019), the different contexts, implementation, technology use and researcher's approach led to different analysis of participant's perception.

Although there is a positive acceptance of online CPD based on the literature, the specific model and practice of Learning Action Cell as implemented by DepEd, coupled with different context of study (TNHS teachers), the technology to be used (Facebook as LMS) and the researcher’s design tools might lead to a different level of teacher’s acceptance. Since there are no studies made known yet in this topic, this gap is addressed through a quantitative study’s purpose to explore TNHS teacher’s acceptability of LAC sessions’ practice based from DepEd’s policy and implementation strategy as online CPD.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this research is a descriptive survey which refers to the gathering of information about prevailing conditions or situations for the purpose of description and interpretation (Salaria, 2012). In this study, samples are given a survey before participating in the Online LAC session, after which, post-survey was administered to find the acceptability rate of online LAC session practice (planning, implementation, evaluation) to TNHS teachers. For the treatment, the participants underwent a one-week online LAC session using Facebook as LMS. The session includes an interactive OER lesson titled “Access to the Internet”, after viewing the lesson, teachers are then encouraged to participate in two discussion forums and one group activity facilitated by two Master of Distance Education student. A researcher-designed Likert-type scale questionnaire is administered before and after the session, and data collected are analyzed using descriptive statistics to show the acceptability rate of Online LAC session practice to TNHS teachers. The sample, instruments used, data collection and analysis of this research are further described in detail below.

Sample

A purposive sampling method is used in this study. This refers to a “non-probability sampling where elements selected for the sample are chosen by the judgment of the researcher (Lavrakas, 2008). 10 out of 82 or 12.20% of the teacher’s population were identified in a memorandum (Appendix B) issued by the school head for all TNHS teachers. However, due to the limited time, only one department with ten Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers were chosen to undergo a pilot testing of Online LAC as directed by the principal. The section below summarizes the demographic details of the subjects where n =10.

Table 1. Socio-demographics variables of TLE teachers where n=10

Socio-demographic variables of TLE teachers		
Gender	Male	30% (n=3)
	Female	70% (n=7)
Age (years)	Mean	38.9
	Median	40
Position	Teacher I	90% (n=9)
	Teacher II	10% (n=1)
No. of years in teaching	Entry Level Teachers (1-5 years)	70% (n=7)
	Experienced Teachers (10-15 years)	30% (n=3)
Highest Educational Attainment	With Masters	80%
	College Graduate	20%
TLE Specialization	Home Economics	50% (n=5)
	Agricultural and Fishery Arts	10% (n=1)
	Industrial Arts	20% (n=2)
	ICT	20% (n=2)

The majority of the respondents were female with 70%, and 30% of the subjects were male. The median age is 40 years old. 90% (n=9) of the subjects are Teacher I and only 10% (n=1) is Teacher II. 70% (n=7) of them are considered as entry-level teachers (1-5 years of experience) while 3 (30%) of the subjects are experienced teachers (10-15 years).

The Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) has four (4) major components, namely: Home Economics (HE), Agriculture and Fishery Arts (AFA), Industrial Arts (IA) and Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Respondents are distributed according to their major with the following percentages: HE is 50% (n=5), AFA 10% (n=1), IA with 20% (n=2), and ICT with 20% (n=2).

Instrumentation

To measure the acceptability of Online LAC sessions practice to TNHS teachers, a researcher-designed Likert-type questionnaire was created. The pre-post survey questionnaire (Appendix C) has three sections: planning, implementation, and evaluation. Under each section, eight questions were developed and a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from “least acceptable” to “very highly acceptable” was used to determine acceptability with a series of questions. Each item was designed to find out if LAC session practice was in place/evident and experienced in a fully-online mode environment, therefore adding the word “Online LAC” to survey questions.

The pre-post survey instrument that was created is based on LAC session standard of practice (Table 4) found on pp. 8-11 of DepEd Order No. 35. Each question developed corresponds the reference from the memorandum as shown on the table below.

Table 4. Bases of LAC Session Practice

Question Content	DepEd Memorandum
Planning	Article III. C. 17. LAC Implementation Process - <i>Before the LAC Session</i> , pp. 8-11
Implementation	Article III. C. 18. LAC Implementation Process - <i>During the LAC Session</i> , p. 11
Evaluation	Article III. C. 19. LAC Implementation Process - <i>After the LAC Session</i> , p. 11

After the survey was developed, five experts on school curriculum and governance operations were asked to review the instrument for any personal bias and other issues. Initially, it was checked by the school head, while one Head Teacher (HT) and two Master Teachers (MTs) reviewed the instrument to check its content on curriculum alignment while a Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) validate its significance on school governance. The reviewers were also asked to check the responsiveness of the researcher-designed tool to teachers’ needs and to determine if all relevant LAC practice has been included in the questionnaire.

Data Collection

The pre-post-survey data were collected from a self-administered online instrument using Google Forms, a survey administration application that allows collection of information from users wherein the information is then collected and automatically connected to a spreadsheet. The pre-survey was administered on February 26, 2019, while post-survey was on March 4, 2019. The test was expected to be taken by the participants for approximately 5-10 minutes. Participants in the study were notified of the test dates via Facebook Messenger group chat, and an invitation was sent to individual teacher’s email for their participation in answering the test/survey via Google Forms. All collected data are stored on the drive and fed to Microsoft Excel for analysis of information.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were coded and transferred to Microsoft Excel to carry out further analysis. The responses collected were analyzed and interpreted based on the objectives of the study. Using Microsoft Excel, quantitative analysis was carried out and the results were tabulated. The analysis of teachers’ perception of the planning, implementation, and evaluation phases of Online LAC using 5-point Likert-scale ranging from 1 (least acceptable) to 5 (very highly acceptable) involved calculating the mean scores, standard deviation, and giving the qualitative verbal interpretation. The pre-survey and post-survey data were also compared according to their mean scores and percentage. The findings of the study are presented in the preceding sections.

DISCUSSION

Result/Findings

The pre-post-surveys were conducted to assess the acceptability of the teachers towards the planning, implementation, and evaluation phases of the Online LAC session practice. The respondents were asked to identify and rate a list of 8 questions on a 5-point Likert scale (where “1” = least acceptable and “5” = very highly acceptable). The mean scores were interpreted using the scale (Table 5) below.

Table 2. Reference Scale for Online LAC Session Interpretation

Rate	Verbal Interpretation	Range
5	Very Highly Acceptable	4.6 – 5.0
4	Highly Acceptable	3.6 – 4.5
3	Acceptable	2.6 – 3.5
2	Moderately Acceptable	1.6 – 2.5
1	Least Acceptable	1.0 – 1.5

Research Question One: How acceptable is Online LAC session “*planning*” to TNHS teachers?

Table 6 shows that the pre-survey mean score of the *planning phase* of Online LAC session is equal to 2.375 with a standard deviation of 0.156 which resulted to a ‘*moderately acceptable*’ perception towards the planning of Online LAC session. However, in the post-survey data, the mean score is 4.675 with a standard deviation of 0.156 which resulted in a ‘*very highly acceptable*’ perception towards the planning of Online LAC session.

Table 6. Planning

Instrumentation Phases	Mean	SD	Qualitative Verbal Interpretation
Pre-survey	2.375	0.156	Moderately Acceptable
Post-survey	4.675	0.156	Very Highly Acceptable

As illustrated in Figure 4, teacher’s acceptability rate for *planning* increases from pre-survey to post-survey by 46% after the Online LAC session.

Figure 1. Graphical Presentation of Online LAC “Planning” Acceptability

Research Question Two: How acceptable is Online LAC session “*implementation*” to TNHS teachers?

Table 7 shows that the pre-survey mean score of the *implementation phase* of online LAC session is equal to 3.050 with a standard deviation of 0.05 which resulted to an ‘*acceptable*’ perception towards the implementation of online LAC session. However, in the post-survey data, the mean score is 4.700 with a standard deviation of 0.10 which resulted in a ‘*very highly acceptable*’ perception towards the implementation of Online LAC session.

Table 7. Implementation Phase

Instrumentation Phases	Mean	SD	Qualitative Verbal Interpretation
Pre-survey	3.050	0.05	Acceptable
Post-survey	4.700	0.10	Very Highly Acceptable

Figure 5 shows teacher’s acceptability rate for implementation increases from pre-survey to post-survey by 33% after the Online LAC session.

Figure 2. Graphical Presentation of Online LAC "Implementation" Acceptability

Research Question Three: How acceptable is Online LAC session "evaluation" to TNHS teachers?

Table 8 shows that the pre-survey mean score of the evaluation phase of Online LAC session is equal to 2.125 with a standard deviation of 0.066 which resulted to moderately acceptable perception towards the evaluation of Online LAC session. However, in the post-survey data, the mean score is 4.675 with a standard deviation of 0.148 which resulted in a very highly acceptable perception towards the evaluation of Online LAC session.

Table 8. Evaluation Phase

Instrumentation Phases	Mean	SD	Qualitative Verbal Interpretation
Pre-survey	2.125	0.066	Moderately Acceptable
Post-survey	4.675	0.148	Very Highly Acceptable

Figure 6 illustrates a 51% increase on teachers’ acceptability rate for *evaluation* on the pre-survey to post-survey after the Online LAC session.

Figure 3. Graphical Presentation of Online LAC "Evaluation" Acceptability

The findings in the descriptive survey presented an overview of the TNHS teachers’ perception in LAC session practice delivered in an online learning environment. TNHS teacher’s acceptability of Online LAC session practice increases after their participation, which shows that the model and structure of Online LAC session based on DepEd memorandum, Simonson’s Equivalency theory, and Anderson’s COI

Framework, with the use of FB as LMS, coupled with content design and interaction activities to present meaningful learning, has delivered a very highly acceptable response.

Limitations of Study

The acceptability of Online LAC session practice to TNHS teachers is explored to gain insights and understanding of a subject potential for a study. With this good intention, comes challenges and limitations that must be taken into considerations to contribute more clarity. This section is an attempt to discuss several issues related to this research.

The sample used in this study is 12.20% of the population using purposive non-probability sampling which means that they do not represent the whole TNHS teachers' acceptability of Online LAC session practice. Also, one department (TLE) may affect survey response results due to the homogeneity of their educational field of experience.

The reliability of the instrument used must also be taken into account. Reliability refers to the consistency or stability of measurement (Kimberlin & Winterstein, 2008). The pre-post survey used in the study has been administered once and has not been through a large sample pilot testing (school-wide). Thus, the consistency of whether it will produce the same results if administered to the same people for a period has not been produced. Therefore, it is recommended that the instruments undergo a scheduled administration to the same sample for identified period to check its reliability and/or subject the instrument to a series of tests for continuous improvement (CI).

One important consideration when doing Online LAC session is to check participant's access to the internet and available technology, gadgets, or other personal devices. In this study, the use of Facebook is chosen for a reason that it can be accessed even without the internet, using mobile data for free. However, mobile data provides limited features, and teachers might not be able to browse the internet to practice the lesson or search for references related to the topic. This study did not include an inquiry of participant's personal available resources and doing an inventory of TNHS teachers' available resources is necessary for a lesson that will be done online.

The decision to implement Online LAC as a one-week session has been done by the discretion of the researchers in consideration of 21st Century Skills and ICT integration in instruction and assessment (Article III. Letter B. 15.4) and from teachers' identified needs based from the consolidated Individual Plan for Professional Development (IPPD) indicating ICT as one of their professional development priorities. However, TNHS teachers' nature of work (6 hours teaching load plus 2 hours administrative tasks) and their limited availability due to added ancillary like coordination deeply affects how, when and where they study. Soliciting participant's time availability and preference through a self-study plan must also be taken into considerations in designing the duration of online LAC session.

Due to limited time, the study does not account the content effectiveness which may be evident by teachers' application of acquired knowledge and skills to their respective classes and an improvement on students' achievements including performances and addressing learning gaps. This should be subjected to further study so as not to fit a "solution" to a problem.

A thorough examination on teachers' demographics such as age differences, types of seminars/trainings/workshops attended, educational attainment, no. of years in teaching, and appointment and promotion should be included and considered for future study and/or packaging of future training for Online LAC. This is important because teachers' exposure could be a factor in the online CPD design and implementation.

The limitations cited are not all-inclusive but may serve as a reference for the study that will contribute to a more comprehensive and helpful way of understanding Online LAC session practice.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Stronge (2007) as cited in p. 2 of Article I. Rationale No. 2 of DO No. 35 s. 2016 identified factors to teachers' success that includes (1) good grasp of content which through learning objectives, 2) ability to select and implement the most effective instructional strategies and materials to cover content objectives, 3) ability to decide on instructional strategies based on formative assessment results, 4) focus on students'

learning and holistic development, and 5) possess a strong professional and work ethics. The same was also considered in the study made by Garbe (pp. 2-3, 2012) stressing the characteristics of effective PD which could impact teachers' progress and learners' development. Thus, in view of teachers' perspective about Online LAC practice, it is highly recommended to systematize or put a systematic mechanism in the adoption of Online LAC as a school-based professional development strategy through *profiling* or *collecting* and *examining of information* as bases for continuous improvement of the Online PD in strengthening of/focus on:

1. *Teacher's Curriculum Needs* by requiring them to participate and contribute to the development and enhancement of curriculum through shared practice (CoP) where their thoughts and voices will be heard about classroom needs, strategies, and best practices. In addition, a mandated periodic collection of department's consolidated reflection logs would be an underlying support of future Online LAC offerings.
2. *Teacher's Professional Development Needs*. Work on regular review and updating of Teacher's IPPD, mapping of teachers' short- and long-term courses taken whether offline and online for better Online LAC design and implementation as well as individual profiling on teachers' ICT skills, available resources, and inventory on personal devices.
3. *School's Professional Development Initiative*. Reinforce School-Based Management (SBM) mechanisms to ensure responsiveness, alignment, and integration of the school's Online LAC initiative to School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Plan (AIP) as evidences necessitate by DO No. 44 s. 2015. Moreover, devising a Manual of Operation about Online LAC could scaffold school leaders to package (design and conduct) Online LACs that are tailored to teachers' interaction preference, scheduling, and other curriculum enhancement needs. Then for continuous improvement, part of the monitoring and evaluation strategy is a review on proposed, identified, developed and implemented Online LAC to be done every 3 years which will serve as a baseline in the design and development of future Online LACs.
4. *School's Manpower Support and Availability of Resources*. Proper support through enough time, provision of resources and acknowledgment (rewards and incentives) will strengthen teachers' participation in Online LAC.
5. *Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanism*. A quarterly visit and evaluation on the minutes of Departmental Online LAC session/s and analysis on its impact to teachers and effectiveness in their curriculum enhancement and classroom management will help leaders, practitioners, and researchers on the improvement of proper mechanisms.
6. *Promotion Developed Online LACs as Matured Technologies*. Flexibility and cost-effectiveness are some of the advantages of Online LAC. Hence, it could be taken by teachers or adopted by schools because it could be taken many times without undergoing the design and development process. Additionally, the Philippine Regulation Commission (PRC) through its accredited CPD provider, DepEd's National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP) recognizes its potential through the Republic Act No. 10912, otherwise known as "The Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Act of 2012. Thus, tried and tested (credible and valid) Online LAC designs, or those reviewed and endorsed by the school curriculum and governance operations team of the Division Office at least 45 days prior to training proper could apply for corresponding credit unit (CU). The effort shall be counted by PRC as CPD points in favor of teachers (Peoples Television, 2018).

These recommendations show how further exploration or study of Online LAC session is needed involving not only the teachers and administrator but must be institutionalized district and division wide.

CONCLUSION

This paper has explored how an online Learning Action Cell Session provided flexibility and options for the study to TNHS teachers. Using a conceptual framework based from DepEd Order No. 35, Simonson's Equivalency Theory and Anderson's COI Framework, equal and meaningful learning using

FB as LMS and content activity interaction has been offered for continuous professional development. This unique model and practice of online LAC session resulted to a very highly acceptable response from TNHS teachers, who from the previous report had difficulty attending classroom LAC session. A quantitative study approach also helps in providing an objective result in teacher's acceptability before and after participating in an online LAC session. In light of this study, some limitations, recommendations, and future research directions must be taken into account in order to better understand the topic and contribute to a more comprehensive finding.

With the advantages of continuous professional learning in online mode comes a responsibility one must take to utilize and maximize its potential. Online education may sound complex and challenging, but according to Ossiannilsson, et. al. (2015, p.3), "when properly planned, designed, and supported by the appropriate mix of technology and pedagogy, is equivalent to, or in certain scenarios more effective than, traditional face-to-face classroom instruction."

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